

detected in the F₂ of crosses among susceptible parents.

Of the eight resistance genes found in IR1905-81-3-1 and IR3259-PP5-160-1, and nine genes in IR3259-PP8-172-7, the

gene conferring resistance to race IH-1 (isolate PO7-10) seems to be linked to the gene resistant to race II-1. The two genes giving resistance to race IB-45 did not segregate independently from the two

genes resistant to race ID-15 or from that acting against race IH-1 (isolate 43); the remaining genes showed no linkage. The six resistance genes in Pai-kan-tao segregated independently. □

Resistance of five IR varieties to tungro

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IR36, IR42, IR50, IR54, and IR56 resistance to tungro was determined by mass screening and test tube inoculation methods.

The five IR varieties and TN1 (susceptible check) were inoculated in a cage with 1, 3, and 4 insects/seedling using the tungro mass screening method. Seedling infection increased as insects increased from 1 to 5/seedling (see figure). TN1 always had the highest percentage of infection, regardless of the number of insects per seedling; followed by IR42, IR36, IR56, and IR50. IR54 showed the lowest seedling infection, but infection level was not significantly different from that of IR50 and IR56.

By the reaction scale for tungro, IR36 and IR42 changed their reaction from resistant to susceptible when the number of insects per seedling was increased from 1 to 5. IR50, IR54, and IR56 reaction changed from resistant to intermediate (see table).

Seven-day-old seedlings were each inoculated with 1, 3, and 5 insects, using the test tube inoculation method. Again, percentage of infected seedlings increased with number of insects per seedling (see figure). However, at even 1 insect/seedling, IR36, IR42, and TN1 were susceptible. IR50, IR54, and IR56 had an intermediate reaction (see table). The highest percentage of infection using the test tube inoculation method, regardless of number of insects, may be caused by the insects' forced feeding on the seedling in confinement.

These results indicate possible unstable tungro resistance in some IR varieties. In the field, degree of resistance decreases with increased disease and insect pressure. This is apparent on varieties with tungro resistance conditioned only by resistance to the vector insect.

Seedling infection (%)

Percentage seedling infection of 5 tungro-resistant IR varieties inoculated with different numbers of tungro-viruliferous *N. virescens* per seedling, following the mass screening and test tube methods of inoculation.

Tungro reaction of 5 IR varieties inoculated by 1, 3, or 5 insects per seedling, following the mass screening and test tube methods of inoculation.^a

Variety	Mass screening			Test tube inoculation		
	1	3	5	1	3	5
IR36	R	I	S	S	S	S
IR42	R	I	S	S	S	S
IR50	R	I	I	I	I	S
IR54	R	R	I	I	I	S
IR56	R	I	I	I	I	S
TN1	I	S	S	S	S	S

^aBased on the scale for RTV mass screening of resistant (R) = 0-30% seedling infection, intermediate (I) = 31-60% seedling infection, susceptible (S) = 61-100% seedling infection.

Reaction of rice varieties to blast and brown spot diseases at Ponnampet

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An experiment at the Ponnampet Agricultural Research Station, during 1982 kharif identified varieties resistant to

blast and brown spot diseases. The National Screening Nursery evaluated 334 entries under nursery and transplanted condition. The nursery followed the uniform blast nursery pattern.

Twenty-eight entries had resistance to blast and brown spot (Table 1). Seventy-eight were resistant to leaf blast 83 to neck blast, and 223 to brown spot (Table 2). □